

Research Article

TEACHING STRATEGIES WITH A FOCUS ON THE STUDENT-CENTERED APPROACH TO LEARNING

Language Teaching

Keywords: learner, teacher, instructional strategy, and methodologies.

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Abstract

A key tactic is to provide high-quality education. The key drivers of high-quality education are instructors, particularly in colleges and universities. Teachers must therefore modify their teaching philosophies and techniques, develop new teaching ideologies, fulfill their own roles, and play their own roles. We should put a strong emphasis on education and enhance the effectiveness of instruction. While education is the goal, teaching is the technique. The amount and nature of learning for all kids can be influenced by the school and teachers. Awareness and enhancing educational processes requires an understanding of teachers' attitudes, actions, and beliefs. They are intimately related to the ways that educators deal with difficulties in their day-to-day work. Numerous elements that affect students' motivation, achievement, and behavior are under the control of educators. They are changing their strategy to put more of an emphasis on developing a supportive learning environment and classroom that is responsive as part of a comprehensive, high-quality education based on children's rights, where there is effective teaching and classroom management, thereby improving students' learning experiences. Because of this, our thesis will discuss the significance of student-centered teaching approaches by outlining their main characteristics in-depth and outlining how they might enhance the learning process.

I. INTRODUCTION

The aim of methodology is to improve any field of education in general and the English language teaching process in particular, by upgrading and enabling teachers' capability in order to be more competent in realizing their goals. Teaching includes long-term exploration, gathering and exchanging of experiences, reconsideration of the old and new ways to enhance it.

Teachers of English as a Second Language (ESL) have been paying attention to investigate their student's needs and their attitudes towards the language they have been studying. They need to inform themselves on the latest trends so that they can play an effective role in the ESL classroom. When teaching a foreign language one of the things that a teacher should have into consideration are the certain qualities which are offered to students who have another native language. So, one should have in mind the problems that students and teachers are facing when learning/teaching a foreign language, such as what teachers have to teach, what the aims of teaching are and how to teach. In order to have a successful teaching, teachers have to motivate students to study, they should help them develop habits through repetition, to keep them interested in, to make a transfer from simple to more complex units in the process of teaching. Also, one should be aware of the following principles (Lado, 1964):

- Speech before writing.
- The development of habits by means of pattern practice.
- The cultural approach.

The first Lado's principle is the so-called *speech before writing* where he claims that the principle applies even when the goal is only to read. Having mastered the basic constructions orally, the student can expand his reading capacity to a higher level of achievement than if he sticks to deciphering script... Students who have mastered the language orally can learn to read more or less readily by themselves or with limited help. Students who have learned to decipher script cannot as a rule learn to speak by themselves. So, if one skill is being mastered, the other skills would not pose such a difficult challenge.

Regarding the *pattern practice* Lado argues that it is a completely oral technique. It consists paradoxically in the conscious substitution of some element other than the chief element being taught so that primary attention is drawn away from it while the entire pattern is repeated. The instructor presents the pattern orally while the students repeat the complete pattern including the substitution. In this way, students' mistakes are more apparent and could be immediately corrected. As for the cultural approach; he claims that last one principle is of great importance as it means the understanding of language in terms of indigenous meaning.

On the other hand, there has been another action-based teaching strategy which argues that no method of teaching foreign speech is likely to be economical or successful which does not include in the first period a very considerable proportion of that type of classroom work which consists of the carrying out by the pupil of orders issued by the teacher (Palmer 1959). While learning, students experience, memorize and understand. They have to have access to available information and materials so they can concentrate on their interaction in the lesson in order to analyze the information. Teachers take active part in giving directions to students' analysis of the information.

Teachers realize that nowadays students learn in different ways, and that methods that are successful for one person does not mean that will be successful for another. Some students prefer to go out and try speaking the foreign language, while others like to listen and then they try to speak. For some mastering the grammar rules is a vital step in laying the basis for learning the foreign language, while others feel better when they find themselves in a situation where they have to use the language, and that is how they are motivated and understand the language's structure. There is no method that can suit all learning styles, so teachers combine different methods in order for students to find the one that is the most appropriate for them and that will help them better understand and learn the foreign language.

II. DEFINING WHAT IS A TEACHING METHOD

The definition of teaching according to the Oxford Learner's Dictionary is explained quite simple as the work of a teacher. And it has really been his/her work to put before the students the subject matter based on his/her knowledge and experience (Oxford Dictionary).

The definition of method also according the Oxford Learner's Dictionary is described as a particular procedure for accomplishing or approaching something, especially a systematic or established one (Oxford Dictionary).

There is a definition on what a teaching method is, such as:

Teaching methods are these forms and procedures through and with which teachers and students acquire their surrounding natural and social reality under institutionalized conditions (Meyer, 1987).

Methods are presented as part of language knowledge for pedagogical purposes and are part of a paradigm, which means a way of creating theories, doing research and providing classroom activities. Actually, L2 methods are a consequence of the application of new theoretical findings. They are also conditioned by educational philosophy, approaches about language nature and what are the ways of its teaching and learning, and conceptions about interaction in the classroom. When these aspects start to change it can be said that a shift of model is taking place (Alcaraz, 1990).

Richards and Rodgers have another distinction regarding the overall concept of what a method is. They mention "*...an umbrella term for specification and interrelation of theory and practice...*" (Richards and Rodgers, 1985)

They refer to the terms approach, design and procedure which comprise the concept of method. They give some definitions in order to clarify the terms.

- *Approach* includes the beliefs and theories regarding language, language learning and teaching that is the base of a method.
- *Design* connects the theories of language and learning in order to create and function of teaching materials and activities held in the classroom.
- *Procedure* deals with techniques and practices used in the ESL classroom as a result of certain approaches and designs (Richards and Rodgers, 1985).

It has been shown that many current issues in language teaching are not particularly new. There are some answers to questions asked often throughout the history of language teaching. It has been estimated that sixty percent of today's world population is multilingual.

It should be mentioned that foreign language learning has always been an important practical concern (Richards and Rodgers, 1986). At first, Latin was the dominant language in the administrative and educational areas, and it kept its role for centuries after the collapse of the Roman Empire and remained the rule in academic and scientific domains well into the 17th and 18th centuries (EC, 2011).

The study of classical Latin and an analysis of the grammar and rhetoric became the model for foreign language study. Students who attended "grammar schools" in the 16th, 17th, and 18th

centuries in England were introduced to the Latin grammar, which consisted of learning grammar rules, translation, conjugations and practice in writing sample sentences, sometimes with the use of parallel bilingual texts and dialogue (Howatt, 1983).

The aim was not speaking the foreign language, and as for the oral practice, students were only reading aloud the sentences they had translated. The sentences were created only to demonstrate the grammar construction of the second language and had nothing in common with the language of actual communication.

Until the 19th century this method, based on the study of Latin, became the standard norm of studying second languages in the classroom. An accent was put on studying the grammar rules and vocabulary via translation and practice in writing selected sentences. Those were sentences translated by students and the only thing that mattered was the grammatical view of them, and had no connection to the real world. No matter of the tries to put some innovations into the language education, it was very complex to change the fact that the classical Latin was the only ideal language that should serve as a sample of how languages should be learnt. All new foreign languages that were taught at school as part of the curriculum were taught based on the Latin method.

All of the exciting topics were transformed into monotonous ones by teachers. Most of the 20th century was under great influence of the grammar-translation method, which included learning a new phrase or a grammatical rule and their translation into students' mother language and memorizing it.

There were strict teaching rules based on things which teachers considered them to be of great importance no matter if they were actually worth learning or not. This was a reason why people had thought that they were not talented to learn a foreign language.

With time, techniques were changing and adapting to more realistic situations, still with grammar and vocabulary taking great representation of the teaching process, but this time into contexts that were more approachable to students. Accent was still put on reading, repeating and memorizing.

The last decades of the 20th century was greatly marked with the development of the communicative approach. The "communicative competence" took the place of the grammatical accuracy and became the main aim of language teaching (Richards and Rodgers, 1986). This new approach was totally opposite of anything else before. It consisted of meeting students' needs in a relaxed classroom atmosphere. It took some time for some of the teachers, who had been practicing using the old techniques, to adapt to the new techniques.

Theoretically or not, English is gaining importance in each aspect of life of the 21st century. In all world areas, the L2 is increasingly finding its way in more primary and secondary schools, people are focusing on sending their children in English-speaking schools, etc. The reasons for this are plenty, such as the information technology, which is becoming the art-of-state profession, is storing its information in English; software for gigantic international companies is available in English; if a person wants to find a better job, together with modern globalization, the

best way is the knowledge of English. The English language becomes part of peoples' everyday life.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Many centuries ago the languages considered as the “official” were Latin and Greek. Afterwards French was taken as a second alternative where second languages were taught. In the mid-19th century took its leading place in the second-languages world. Before that period, the Classical Method of teaching took place based on repetition drills and translations of the ancient texts. Communication skills have become increasingly important to those who were in need or simply wanted to learn a second language in the 1940s, since then a lot of theories started to appear. A foreign language taught in school arises the question which teaching methods should be used for this purpose, which certainly is not quite so simply to answer.

It might be expected that linguists and educators could just give the answers, but is there a conceptual framework guaranteeing that the same established methods of ESL teaching could actually work in several different countries? Unfortunately, there is no such framework.

Different students require more than just one method to be used at once. The trend has been directed towards combining more methods and maybe it is the best solution because it includes many learning styles. It enables teachers to choose between methods for they know which method in certain period is the most suitable for students' needs, choosing the best out of each method and implementing it into the L2 classroom.

Mori (1999) insisted for teachers to focus more on student in-class assessments in order to match teaching methods with student beliefs. Her research was concentrated on L2 learner beliefs on learning and its connection to L2 acquisition, claiming that their beliefs cannot be restricted to only one theory. The conclusion from her study are that students' beliefs are multidimensional and complicated, i.e. L2 acquisition and learning are not related, and that teachers have to be aware of learner beliefs to provide efficient classroom guidance.

Another study, Green's (1993), included quantitative information to find out whether students enjoyed tasks which emphasized language content or language correctness, and how would they react to new teaching methods. Green made a conclusion that students did not consider that the method with language correctness was of a great help. Besides, his results argued that students were not against using new methods. Yet, his data did not if students liked the fun activities. He concluded that the results were not decisive, but could add to future studies that would try to recognize what teachers want to teach and what students would enjoy to learn.

Studies made by August and Shanahan (2006) have shown that the lack of appropriate literacy skills represents a big challenge. Some researchers, such as Valdés, Bunch, Snow, Lee, and Matos (2005) claimed that one of the issues for English-language learners is that the center of language instruction lies in teaching and learning unnoticed skills set aside from the core

curriculum. There are other requirements for students and teachers. Teachers who have good knowledge and are qualified in teaching English will have to "...demonstrate knowledge of the language of instruction to levels consistent with demands of the literacy and content standards" (Brisk and Proctor, 2012).

L2 teachers still have much to learn and work on their techniques and teaching methods, knowledge, and preparation to be as effective as possible. Danielson (2007) has argued that teacher quality of success and of teaching are powerful elements of students' success. However, there are other points that will help students learn the foreign language. Some of the most relevant points are (i) the various academic, social, and linguistic skills among students; (ii) the limited knowledge and competences of the teacher when it comes to teaching L2; and (iii) the lack of knowledge in preparing and applying excellent programs for English students (Guofang and Edwards, 2010). These are the three factors which represent a big challenge for successful education of students.

In the work of Tamura (2016), it is emphasized that the basic form of instruction in class is lesson which has its own function. First of all, it helps students with gaining and conquering new habits and abilities, with the opportunity of understanding, speaking, reading and writing English. There are lessons that communicate knowledge (1), lessons of developing skills, and reinforcing knowledge (2), combined lessons (3), lesson of revision (4) and lessons of verification the knowledge and appreciation of the effort (5) done by the students.

In his work, Sierra (2016) provides a critical assessment of the role that methods have in the educational process, with a certain turn to the different methods used in the foreign language teaching today. Knowledge of different methods gives teachers a good background reference to their own stand on pedagogical matters and classroom practice, and in addition helps them understand the process that the second language has undergone. Teaching is not static, but changing in order to respond to the new needs and demands as teachers, applied linguists and educationists can prove. Grandgent (1918) argues that it was natural for teachers, having no other model to rely to, to adopt the plan that was already set in the textbooks for Greek and Latin. In this method, the classical one, students put accent on rules, exceptions and other things which differ from the natural method which is an impulse, rather than a plan; and its products depend, to a greater extent to those of any other school, on the personality of the instructor. No matter which of the methods is being used as long as teachers find them effective and efficient in their classroom, and which also influence students' foreign language acquisition. Combining and implementing these methods one at a time is also beneficial for both, teachers because their work is alleviated and students because they do not struggle while learning the L2.

Mora (2008) discussed about some crucial teaching methods of L1 teaching. Those methods are:

- Grammar-Translation Method;
- Direct Method;
- Reading Method;
- Audio-Lingual Method;
- Community Language Learning;
- The Silent Way;
- Communicative Language Teaching;
- Total Physical Response.

Each of these shall be separately examined and discussed in order to understand their role and action, and also how do they influence students and help teachers at the same time in the English-speaking classroom.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The nature of this study is descriptive and comparative, therefore in providing detailed description of each teaching method, we will try to explain their advantages and the possible disadvantages and in this way we can have a better overview of what are the most appropriate approaches for a given classroom.

The main aims of this study is to look at the different teaching methods, to see their advantages and disadvantages, differences and similarities, and to give some solutions regarding new methods which teachers could employ in their English-language classroom.

It is certainly not easy for teachers, nor is for students. Each student responds differently to teaching methods. Ones react to one kind of method, while others to another. A common problem for them is the low knowledge of the basics of the English language. So, more or less, they interact with their teacher using their previously established vocabulary and grammar rules. They also face teacher's creativity, or not, in presenting the subject in the ESL classroom.

This study will have to answer the following questions:

1. How teachers should teach?
2. What are the aims of teaching in a student-centered environment?
3. How a student should be involved?

Therefore it is important to have in mind the following issues:

1. There are many differences between teaching methods.
2. Teachers have to be certain in the aim of teaching in a student-centered classroom.
3. There have to be certain principles to which teachers should comply with.

V. TEACHING METHODS

5.1 Grammar-Translational Method

The grammar-translational method was the dominant foreign language teaching method in Europe from the 1840s to the 1940s and it is still being used in some parts of the world. Somewhere in the middle of the 19th century, theorists were questioning its principles. Changes were taking place. Due to the increased need to speak foreign languages, some people started to examine the nature of the language. Among them are C. Marcel and F. Gouin, as well as T. Pendergast. Marcel accentuated the importance of understanding meaning in language learning, while Pendergast proposed the first structural syllabus. He proposed arranging grammatical structures so the easiest were taught first. Gouin thinks that children learned languages through using language for a sequence of related actions. He worked on presenting each item in the text and using gestures to boost verbal meaning (cited in Richards and Rodgers, 2014). Although these suggestions had some influence, they did not become a prerogative or last long. There were no public media so as to spread their ideas and they were left in oblivion.

The grammar-translational method is consisted of teaching the L2 grammar. Its principles according Larsen-Freeman (1986) are emphasizing the translation from into the target language. Classes are taught in the mother tongue, with little active use of the target language. These aims are achieved in the classroom by long and elaborate grammatical explanations and demonstrations in the native language (Rivers, 1968). Greater part of the vocabulary is learnt as isolated words. Nation and Gu(2001; 2003) agree that vocabulary learning by word lists is an effective way of learning vocabulary. Reading and writing are the main skills. Other characteristic of the grammar-translational method was that teachers are dominant figures in the L2 classroom and the interaction is mainly based between teacher-student; the basic unit is the sentence; too much attention is paid to the mother language and is used to compare with the foreign language. Speaking or listening are not that popular in this kind of teaching method.

This method has been under some attacks from various people. It has been criticized that it creates frustration for students as they have to learn pointless grammar use and vocabulary, and it could never release the learner from L1, and also the communicative aspect of this method is being reduced to a low level.

Despite of these attacks, the method is still used because there is no great distinction between the grammar and communicative approach; instead they sometimes complement each other, and otherwise increase students' awareness of the form and structure of L1.

Summarizing the advantages of this method is that it is the easiest and shortest way of explaining the meaning of words and phrases. Students also don't have any issues understanding the lesson because it is on L1. And it is very practical for the teachers as he carries out everything in L1. On the other side the negative aspect is that students lack interaction in the classroom. Also very little attention is paid to communication and the translation of the sentence structures is misleading.

Due to the disadvantages, educators tried to find another way to correct the gaps of the method, and that is how the Direct Method came into question.

5.2 Direct Method

The Direct Method, also called Natural Method, was established in Germany and France around 1900 (Brown, 2000). The direct method is a crucial change from the Grammar-Translational Method because the L2 is used as a tool for communication in the English-speaking classroom, and the usage of L1 and translation as a learning technique are minimized. There is a transition from using the literary language to the spoken everyday language. This method represents a first attempt to ease the language learning situation.

Teachers became frustrated with students who could not interact orally, so it led to the development of new different techniques. This includes using pictures and objects, questioning and answering, dictation and imitation, etc. The idea was that non-native language teaching has to be the same as students learn their native language.

Larsen-Freeman (2004) talked about few techniques of Direct Method.

Question and answer exercise. This exercise is conducted only in the target language. Students are asked questions and answer in full sentences so that they practice new words and grammatical structures. They have the opportunity to ask questions as well as answer them.

Self-correction. This technique has some important advantages, such as:

- students are involved in the process – this renews confidence if they can correct themselves;
- self-corrected mistakes are more memorable and less likely to occur;
- it encourages learner independence;
- it gives the teacher feedback on the student's knowledge, ability and awareness.

Summarizing the advantages of the Direct Method it is clear that it is altered from the grammar-translational method. One of the promising things is that it teaches the languages and not about it. It has the same principles of teaching as the native language is taught. And not only has that, as a contrast of the grammar-translational method, here the speaking made it more attractive for those who want to pay attention to communication in the L2.

Yet, the direct method, despite of its advantages, has not made it into the educational system. Its disadvantage was that it was difficult to implement it into public schools. Brown argues that the Direct Method “did not take well in public education where the constraints of budget, classroom size, time, and teacher background made such a method difficult to use” (Brown, 1994). Due to the fact it did not become popular in the beginning of the 20th century, the stage was set for the Audio-Lingual Method.

5.3 Audio-Lingual Method

The Audio-Lingual method of teaching had its origins during World War II when it became known as the Army Method. It is also called the Aural-Oral Method. It is based on the structural view of language and the behaviorist theory of language learning. The Audio-Lingual Approach to language teaching has a lot of similarities with the Direct Method. Both were considered as a reaction against the shortcomings of the Grammar Translation Method, both reject the use of the mother tongue and both stress that speaking and listening competences preceded reading and writing competences. But there are also some differences. The direct method highlighted the teaching of vocabulary while the audio-lingual approach focus on grammar drills (Audio-lingual Method, n.d.).

This method appeared as a product of linguistics, psychology, and politics. In the 1940s, linguists from the University of Michigan and other universities had the task of finding materials for teaching English to foreign students. Their solution was mainly based on contrastive analysis of the L1 and L2, which they considered would settle all the difficulties in acquiring the language.

The Audio-Lingual Method is generally an oral approach, just like the Direct Method. However, it differs from the Direct Method in many respects. Lessons consisted of oral drilling of grammatical structures and pronunciation. It became largely known as the Oral Approach, Aural-Oral Approach or the Structural Approach. Foreign language can be learned and taught more effectively if it is presented in spoken form before students will see written form. “Aural-Oral training is needed to provide the foundation for the development of other language skills” (Richards & Rodgers, 1987). It views language as a composition of semantic structures and the syllabus is organized around these structures. Another thing is that all natural languages first developed orally, like listening and speaking before reading and writing. So this is the rule for the Audio-Lingual Method. Avoiding students to written language is believed to help developing

correct pronunciation. Afterwards come the reading and writing of the material that had been previously learned orally.

Acquiring a foreign language is a mechanical process. So memorization and repetition of dialogues or other drill patterns minimize the risk of making a mistake and increase the possibilities of answering correctly. While the Direct Method emphasizes learning vocabulary through implementing it in situations, the Audio-Lingual Method drills using grammatical sentence patterns. Therefore, drills and pattern practice, mimicry and so on are typical of this method (Richards, 1987). Listening and speaking took the main stage of the method.

The objective of the method is precise pronunciation and grammar, responding quickly and accurately while speaking and owing sufficient vocabulary to use with grammar structures. Emphasis was put to mastering and learning the rules of how to combine them. The main activities consisted of reading dialogues, repetition of model sentences and drilling patterns. The point was students to imitate as much as possible the teacher in the English-speaking classroom. And also worth mentioning is the target language which is the only language used in the classroom

Summarizing the advantages of the Audio-Lingual Method it is clear that its objectives are developing listening and speaking and also using visual aids which helps in vocabulary teaching. On the other side, this method was also criticized a lot. First, its theoretic foundation was attacked as being unsound both in terms of language theory and learning theory by Chomsky's theory of TG grammar; second, the practical results fell short of expectations and students were often found to be unable to transfer skills acquired through Audiolingualism to real communication outside the classroom. Therefore, it ignores the communicative competence in teaching practice (Liu and Shi, 2007).

5.4 Silent Way

In the beginning of the 1960s, students had a difficulty in transferring the habits they had mastered in the Audio-Lingual classroom to communicate outside it. Chomsky (1964) argued that speakers should know the basic abstract rules, by which they understand and create novel utterances. That is how language acquisition no longer had habit formation as a rule, but instead rules formation.

Gattegno, founder of the Silent Way Method, took into consideration the way children learn their native language and based on that he developed a method. He believed that learning a foreign language is the same as babies and young children learn their mother language. In this process students mobilize their inner resources such as their perception, awareness, cognition, imagination, intuition, creativity, etc. While they learn a language, they integrate anything new into themselves, and use it for further learning (Gattegno, 1976). He argues that this method is constructivist and inquires students to develop their own conceptual models of all areas of the language. This could be done by letting students be experimental learners.

Attention should be paid to the word “silent” as it is based on the theory that the teacher should be silent in the English-language classroom and let the student produce as much language as possible.

Gattegno thought that students should create independence, autonomy, and responsibility (Gattegno, 1972). While students solve language problems, they have to cooperate with each other. A teacher, who is a stimulator, is silent greater part of the time and they have to oppress their instinct to correct even slightest mistake. Even in correcting mistakes, the teacher could help at least with a verbal answer, but the main point here is that learner is the main actor.

Richards and Rodgers (1986) summarized the theory of learning behind the Silent Way:

- Learning is facilitated if the learner discovers or creates rather than remembers and repeats what is to be learned.
- Learning is facilitated by accompanying (mediating) physical objects.
- Learning is facilitated by problem solving involving the material to be learned.

Summarizing the advantages it is easy to see that acquiring L2 through problem solving is especially good because it uses creativity, discovery, increases intelligence and good memory. Teacher’s role is limited to giving minimum correction, remaining silent, leaving the student to solve the language problems and understand its mechanism. And the student himself/herself figures out and testes how language works. In this case, learning takes the leading role in comparison to teaching. The disadvantages of the Silent Way is that it is been considered as a raw method. The student works alone and there is a lack of communication in the classroom. The help from the teacher is minimal, and additional material used in this method cannot include all language aspects, which implies usage of extra materials.

5.5 Community Language Learning

After Chomsky’s linguistic revolution (Chomsky, 1957), linguists and foreign language teachers left the audio-lingual method which saw language as a composition of semantic structures. New methods were developed in order to solve the disadvantages of the audio-lingual method. One of these became largely known as the Community Language Learning or Communicative Approach. The aim of the method is to make communicative competence crucial element of language teaching and generates procedures for teaching the four skills. This method encourages real communication and performs important assignments. Language learners supposed to be negotiators, while teachers have the roles of organizers, guides, counselors, etc. The model is based on counseling techniques which smoothens disturbance, threat and other issues student faces while L2 acquiring. The community language learning is different than the other methods. It is the

prominent language teaching in many countries as it makes L2 learning fun, exciting, and also helps students generate linguistic and communicative competence.

Curran and his coworkers created the method. In the “counseling-learning” educational model, students are considered to be a group in need of counseling. There are couple of conditions that have to be met in order for learning to take place (Curan, 1976).

- Members should interact in an interpersonal relationship.
- Students and teachers work together to facilitate learning by
 - valuing each other,
 - lowering the defense that prevent interpersonal interaction,
 - reducing anxiety,
 - and constituting a supportive community.
- Teachers’ role is that of a true counselor.
 - They are not perceived as a threat,
 - They don’t impose boundaries and limits,
 - They concentrate on the learners needs.

Summarizing the advantages of the Community Language Learning it is clear that there are some good points regarding the previously mentioned teaching methods, such as counselor allowing students to choose the type of conversation, their confidence boosts, etc. On the other hand, issues also aroused, like could the method be used at all levels in teaching or how appropriate is it for non-native teachers? The teacher can become non-directive, and students are often in need of directions.

5.6 Total Physical Response

Language teachers have noticed the value of connecting language to physical activity. Asher, a professor of psychology, developed a teaching technique based on coordination and action, which is the Total Physical Response (TPR) (Asher, 1977). He concentrated on couple of features so as to develop the method. He wanted to access a stress-free method, where students would not be anxious. The method also combines information and competences via using kinesthetic sensory system. Therefore, it is much easier for students to quickly gather information and competences. As a consequence, this leads to a great motivation. The aim is understanding the L2 prior to speaking. It is not expected for the student to start to talk immediately, instead there is a preparation period while he/she spontaneously begin using the L2 and is certain in his/her skills.

Students have to understand a great deal of input before they could learn how to interact. Then when they are still young, students receive input in which a lot of physical manipulation and action is involved (Nunan, 1991). The connection between movement and language alleviates learning due to the connection between stimulus and response. In this regard, the approach has a perceptive audio-lingual direction. Although this method relies on the structured psychology, its linguistic direction is different from that of Krashen and Terrell’s, and there is a structuralist or grammatical position behind this method (Sanchez, 1997).

In the TPR classroom, students usually listen and act, while the teacher is in charge of the performance. As Asher claimed that “The instructor is the director of a stage play in which the students are the actors” (Asher, 1977).

The Total Physical Response has its own flaws like every other method. It had proven to be very efficient in the beginning levels, but as soon as students were advancing with their learning, the TPR lost its uniqueness.

Summarizing the advantages of the TPR it can be concluded that when used with other methods it can create incredible results. Also it is of great help to teachers as the TPR is convenient with other teaching methods. It attracts attention to comprehension, and it also emphasizes the meaning instead the form. Unlike that, the TRP is more suitable with the beginning phases of language acquisition. It is suitable to use it in association with other techniques and methods and represents a useful tool for teaching L2.

5.7 Reading Method

In the early decades of the 20th century, based on the Coleman Report (Coleman, 1929), the reading method was endorsed to language teaching by the Modern Language Association of America. As could be seen from the work of the Western countries, the method set up in North America until the late 1930s and early 1940s (West, 1941). As English became an international language, it requires all the people to master it. One of the factors which leads to successful teaching of English is the Reading Method.

This method helps students to solve their reading problems. The method improves students’ knowledge and learns something new because they are required to read. Reading is an active skill which involves guessing, predicting, etc. By reading students will learn about the tenses, the grammar, how to use them, and so on. They will also get familiar with correct pronunciation of words, and not to mention the benefits that will come afterwards.

The reading method has a lot in common with the Grammar Translation Method since it gives stress to written skills. Students learn only the grammar because it is essential for reading comprehension and fluency. But teachers anyway considered it to be a flexible method.

In the classroom, students usually translate the text, deduce the meaning of unknown words or phrases, while teachers create situations in which students are most suggestible and afterwards they present the material by encouraging positive effects in students. The students figure out how to pronounce each word in the text and instantly understand its meaning, just like L1. Translation reappears in this approach as a respectable classroom procedure related to comprehension of the written text (Mora, 2012).

It is also time-saving method as students all read at the same time. The method also has shortcomings because there is no such a teaching method named as the most efficient based on its curriculum, motivation, number of students, etc. The method pays particular attention on the written skill and lacks the speaking one, while the vocabulary and the grammar are controlled.

5.8 Suggestopedia

Suggestopedia, often considered as the strangest method, was developed in the 1970s by the Bulgarian educator Georgi Lozanov. The name of Suggestopedia is a combination of the words *suggestion* and *pedagogy*. Suggestopedia has been used in various fields but its most common use has been in the field of foreign languages. The method helps students learn a language three to five times faster than with a conventional method. The theory used positive suggestion in teaching during its development in the 1970s. Today, certain elements of the method are contained in good practice. The original form of Suggestopedia by Lozanov consisted of very long dialogues altogether with vocabulary lists and some grammatical points. The dialogues were read to students accompanied with a famous piece of music in the background. The teacher acts in the rhythm of music, and students can focus on the music, the text or combination of the two.

A second, not so formal reading would use not so impressive piece of music, and it would take less important role. During both types of reading, students would sit in comfortable seats, other than the classical classroom ones in a stimulating atmosphere regarding the design and lightning. After the readings of the dialogues accompanied by music, the teacher will use the dialogues for more conventional work. In theory, the dialogues will be adopted by students during the reading due to the relaxed and laid-back atmosphere and the positive suggestion developed by the music.

However, this method is not supported by evidence. There have been criticisms that classical music is not created for everyone's ear, and it is more of irritating than relaxing. Other thing is that the length of dialogues can confuse rather to stimulate students, and for last the relaxed atmosphere with the armchairs will surpass the means of the educational institutions.

5.9 Bilingual Method

Bilingualism is commonly defined as the use of at least two languages by an individual (ASHA, 2004). Lam (2001) claims that "bilingualism refers to the phenomenon of competence and communication in two languages". It is difficult to decide what the key factor in at least two languages is. How a person knowing two or more languages learn the meanings of words to which he/she attaches the linguistic representation in the other language.

The bilingual method works with L1 and L2. The method starts as bilingual and at the end it transfers into monolingual. The teacher uses the native and the non-native languages in the ESL class. This is a combination of the Direct Method and the Grammar-Translation Method.

The aims of the method are to make the learners fluent and accurate while speaking the foreign language. It also aims at making learners accurate at writing and preparing them to master the bilingualism.

The writing and reading skills are incorporated early in the learning phase with introduction of the skills of speaking and writing. Also, L1 is not used as a translation, instead all the focus is on L2.

This method is especially acceptable for an average English teacher without any special preparation following a previously settled pattern. A great amount of time is saved with this method as teacher only gives the meaning in the mother tongue of the student and the rest of the time is used for giving pattern practice. It also improves fluency and accuracy.

The Bilingual method does not require any teaching resources and is acceptable for all kinds of educational institutions.

VI. STUDENT-CENTERED APPROACH

Student-centered methods are deemed best practice in situations where the teaching objectives for the lesson include acquisition of independent study skills, greater student autonomy, working collaboratively with others, the construction of knowledge from firsthand experience, and the application of basic academic skills for authentic purposes. Most student-centered methods are concerned not only with knowledge construction but also the development of effective learning strategies, often encompassed by the expression ‘learning how to learn’. In areas such as science for example, a student-centered investigative approach is designed to give students firsthand experience of the scientific inquiry process as well as building conceptual knowledge. In student-centered approaches the *process of learning* is often considered more important than the acquisition of factual knowledge.

Teaching methods that are described as ‘student-centered’ are aligned with the constructivist theory of learning – although some of these methods were in operation long before constructivism emerged as a coherent theory. Student-centered approaches have been given specific titles by their creators (e.g., activity-based learning, guided discovery; inquiry approach; problem-based learning; project-based learning; situated learning) but the principles and practices associated with the methods are very similar. The subtle differences among the methods described below are usually associated with the amount of guidance and structure provided by the teacher during the learning process, and with the degree of autonomy demanded of the learners. The underlying principles for most of the methods are that:

- students should be actively involved in the learning process and intrinsically motivated
- topics, issues, or subject matter should be interesting, relevant and intrinsically motivating
- whenever possible, learning experiences should take place in real-life situations where the relevant knowledge and skills will really be needed and used (situated learning).

Student-centered approaches and the contexts in which they can be used, can be addressed under the general categories of inquiry-based methods, project-based or resourced-based learning and computer-assisted learning.

6.1 Inquiry-based methods

North Carolina Department of Instruction presents a document called ‘Why Inquiry?’ on its website. Referring to science education, the writer neatly encapsulates the purposes of inquiry in these terms: Students in all grades and in every scientific discipline should have the opportunity to ask questions, plan and conduct investigations, use appropriate tools and techniques to gather data, think critically and logically about relationships between evidence and explanations, and communicate arguments. Students who learn to question, debate, or explore acquire a deeper understanding of the world. By discovering principles, rather than just memorizing them, students learn not just what we know, but how we know it, and why it is important.

This category of teaching method includes discovery learning, problem based learning, project work, and resource-based learning.

6.2 Discovery learning

Discovery learning is perhaps the best-known form of inquiry-based learning. It requires students to investigate a topic, issue or problem by active means, obtain pertinent information, interpret causes and effects where relevant, and arrive at conclusions or solutions (Ormrod, 2000). The method is particularly appropriate for achieving important objectives in social studies, science, geography, history, health, environmental education and mathematics. The general consensus regarding discovery learning is that it is most effective when:

- the process is carefully structured
- students have prerequisite knowledge and skills
- teachers provide any necessary support during the investigations.

Discovery learning takes many different forms, ranging from open ended, minimally-guided investigation through to fairly tightly structured ‘guided discovery’ where the teacher still retains a fair degree of control (Kirschner et al., 2006; Zion et al., 2007). In methods involving open ended discovery the teacher may provide all necessary resource materials but learners are given little or no direction for carrying out their investigations.

They must decide for themselves the most appropriate method for tackling the investigation and must then reach their own conclusions from the observations they make. With this unstructured approach the outcomes are sometimes not very good, particularly for students with poor study skills and difficulties with inductive reasoning.

Guided discovery, on the other hand, has a much tighter structure. The teacher usually explains the lesson objectives to the students, provides initial input or explanation to help students begin the task efficiently, and may offer suggestions for a step-by-step procedure to find out the target information or to solve the problem.

During the activities, the teacher may make suggestions, raise questions, or provide hints. This form of ‘scaffolding’ keeps students on track and ensures that understanding, rather than confusion, is achieved. Providing scaffolding can help to reduce the overall cognitive load associated with this form of learning (Schmidt et al., 2007). Guided discovery is generally regarded as a motivating method, enjoyed by learners (Adkisson & McCoy, 2006).

A typical guided discovery learning session takes the following format:

- A topic is identified or an issue is posed; for example, what can we find out about magnets?
- Teacher and students work together to brainstorm ideas for ways of investigating the topic.
- Students work individually or in small groups to obtain and interpret data.
- Inferences and tentative conclusions are drawn, shared across groups and modified if necessary.
- Teacher clears up any misconceptions, summarizes the findings and helps to draw conclusions.

6.3 Problem-based learning

Problem-based learning (PBL) is sometimes referred to more accurately as ‘issues-based’ learning, because many of the topics used for study are not really ‘problems’. The method has gained popularity in recent years as highly suitable for use in higher education contexts; but PBL can also be used in upper primary, middle, and secondary schools if the issues to be explored are selected carefully, ensuring that they are age-appropriate and relevant. King (2001) states: PBL offers a mode of learning which might be considered closer to real life.

This real-life link is twofold: firstly, the projects or problems used often reflect or are based on real-life scenarios; secondly, the processes of team working, research, data collection, critical thinking and so on are those which will be of use to the students in their further careers.

Similarly, Lee (2001) has suggested that, ‘Learning through problem solving may be much more effective than traditional didactic methods of learning in creating in the student’s mind a body of knowledge that is useful in the future’.

In PBL, students are presented with a real-life issue that requires a decision, or with a real-life problem that requires a solution. With older learners, the problem or issue is often intentionally left ill defined and ‘messy’ so that there is no clear path or procedure to follow. Students typically work in small collaborative groups. The teacher or tutor has the role of general facilitator of the group discussion, but does not direct or control the investigative process.

6.4 Project-based learning

Project-based learning in various forms and at various levels of sophistication has been popular for very many years and represents another approach to student-centered learning based on constructivist principles. The simplest form is the well known ‘project method’ used in primary and secondary schools when students work individually or collaboratively to gather and present information on a chosen topic (e.g., transport; the Second World War; butterflies; China, etc.). But projects are now becoming more ambitious and focused on real-life issues and problems that can be investigated. Indeed, there is a tendency for education writers to use the terms project-based and problem-based almost interchangeably.

According to Thomas (2000), ‘Project-based learning [utilizes]... complex tasks, based on challenging questions or problems that involves students in design, problem-solving, decision making, or investigative activities, give students the opportunity to work relatively autonomously over extended periods of time, and culminate in realistic products or presentations’. The key features are that the content or focus of the study is authentic; the students are encouraged to think and reason independently, the work may involve cooperation and collaboration with others and may or may not involve the use of ICT. One of the advantages of integrating information technology into project work is that students can learn both ICT skills and specific content knowledge simultaneously.

Thomas (2000) suggests that learning that arises from project work tends to be retained more readily than learning acquired as a result of didactic teaching methods. Such learning is also seen as being more flexible and adaptable to new situations. Thomas, who includes problem-based methods in his review of project-based learning, also states that the methods ‘... equivalent to, or slightly better than, other models of instruction for producing gains in general academic achievement and for developing lower-order cognitive skills in traditional subject matter areas’.

5.5 Resource-based learning

Although there are many different definitions of resource-based learning (RBL), the approach is usually described as a methodology that allows students to learn from their own active processing of information using a range of authentic resources. Students learn effective skills for using library catalogues, making electronic searches, using CD-ROMs, making telephone calls to

seek information, conducting interviews, sending and receiving emails, and writing letters. These skills are valuable for autonomous learning. Some of the skills may need to be taught initially by more direct forms of instruction.

RBL is suited to most areas of the school curriculum. One of its primary goals is to foster students' autonomy in learning by providing opportunities for them to work individually or collaboratively while using appropriate resources and applying relevant literacy, numeracy and study skills to explore interesting topics.

In many ways, resource-based learning shares many characteristics with project-based learning. In both methods the students use books, community publications, reports, videos, DVDs, online material and human resources to obtain information relating to a chosen or set topic that they must collate, analyze, critique and consolidate into an appropriate form for presentation.

5.6 Computer-assisted learning

In several places above, mention has already been made of the contribution that computers and information technology can make within a constructivist approach; for example, when students are independently searching for information to complete a project or to solve a problem. Computers in the classroom have provided learners and their teachers with fast and easy ways of accessing information, communicating electronically with others, and producing high quality written work and graphics. Computers can also deliver instructional programs covering virtually any area of the Curriculum and geared to any age or ability level. Computer software for educational purposes includes not only 'drill and practice' programs (used mainly in tutorial or remedial contexts for building students' skills in areas such as phonics, reading, arithmetic, or spelling) but also interactive instructional programs presenting factual information, simulations and role-play, problem-solving activities, video clips, and of course computer games.

Computers and their associated software present great opportunities for motivating students, encouraging independent learning, and for improving the quality of educational programs. The use of ICT continues to grow rapidly in schools, with increasing numbers of students also having access to a personal computer at home.

CONCLUSION

Teacher effectiveness is not concerned with any particular teaching *method*. Rather, it is concerned in a more general sense with the way in which teachers operate in their classrooms – the decisions they make, the actions they take, their interactions with students, their presentation skills, and the way they manage the group.

There are five areas in which skilled teachers display their expertise. These areas include presenting and explaining subject matter and ideas, questioning students during lesson time, giving feedback, strategy training and adapting or differentiating instruction.

Effective classroom teaching, as with formal lecturing, requires *clarity* in the teacher's presentations. Poor explanations usually get students utterly confused and therefore create learning problems. This lack of clarity maybe due to a failure to communicate effectively at the students' language and ability level, using complex terminology, failing to draw analogies or give examples to which students can relate, giving instructions out of sequence, inadequate use of visual support material, presenting too much information at one time, not making relationships clear, and failing to check for understanding.

Explaining need not (and should not) be a one-way process. A good explanation requires questions directed to the students to ensure that what is being said is making sense; and students should be encouraged to ask the teacher questions during and after an explanation. Perhaps the least helpful question for a teacher to ask (but one that is frequently heard) is 'Do you understand that?' Very few students, especially those who lack confidence and those not doing well, are going to confess in front of the entire class that they don't understand.

Teachers have to plan and prepare educational activities that engage students in debates and discussions on various topics related to their everyday life and interests, to be innovative in their lectures and to commit themselves to contributing to the development of the student. They have to emphasize communication and interaction, to change the conventional passivity in the classroom while the lesson is active. Seeing the other more active students, even the weakest ones might gain confidence and take part in the lesson using the L2.

A good teacher knows when to step back and leave the students lead the class and stay in the background monitoring. A good teacher also knows when to be spontaneous and improvise and thus making the ESL classroom more flexible in dealing with unexpected situations.

On the other hand, by using the principles teachers will have more time and energy. Effective teaching involves requiring certain knowledge about students and using it to design the teaching method. When teachers teach, they do not only teach the content, they teach students the content. Various students' features influence learning the foreign language. Their age, cultural background, prior knowledge leads students to approach acquiring the L2 in different ways. As soon as the teacher gathers the most significant information, he/she can plan and design the lessons adhering identification of common misconceptions, recognition of additional practice, etc.

Effective teaching includes assessments and learning objectives. Teaching is more effective and learning a foreign language is easier when there are learning objectives, such as the non-native language acquired at the end of the school year, and assessments, such as tests,

dictations, etc. Effective teaching also includes using suitable teaching roles to uphold the learning purposes. The role teachers assume is of great importance as it serves as a guideline for students' thinking and behavior.

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